

IMPROVING STUDENT'S READING SKILLS THROUGH ACTIVITY BASED LEARNING

Gadoev Doston Zokir ugli,
master's degree student, SamSIFL
AbduvaitovSanjarbek Said ugli,
master's degree student, SamSIFL

Abstract: Reading involves comprehending written material. It is a difficult task that calls for both perception and thought. Word recognition and comprehension are two connected reading processes. The process of determining how written symbols correspond to one's native language is referred to as word recognition. Making understanding of words, sentences, and related text constitutes the process of comprehension. To understand written content, readers often employ a variety of skills, including prior knowledge, vocabulary, grammatical proficiency, familiarity with texts, and others. Practices and exercises in the classroom encourage the application of a balanced strategy to enhancing students' reading comprehension. This study presents a few strategies and techniques that guarantee the growth of readers' word recognition, reading fluency, and planning of classroom activities to encourage students' internal motivation for reading..

Key words: Classroom activities, comprehension, authentic reading texts, reading skills.

Reading assignments for class and homework must resemble (or be) authentic reading tasks that need meaningful conversation if educators want their students to build communicative competence in reading. Therefore, they must be true in three different ways.¹

¹Pearson, P. David. "The Roots of Reading Comprehension Instruction". <http://www.postgradolinguistica.ucv.cl>. University of California, Berkeley. Retrieved 15 March 2013.

1. The reading materials must be genuine; they must be the kinds of books that students will want to read and need to be able to read whether they are on vacation, studying abroad, or utilizing the language in other situations outside of the classroom.

When choosing texts for student assignments, keep in mind that a reading text's level of difficulty depends less on its language and more on the conceptual challenge and the task(s) that students are required to complete. When a text is made simpler by altering the language, natural repetition is frequently removed, which makes it more challenging for pupils to predict how the text will be organized. In actuality, using the original actually makes a piece more challenging to read.

Making a text more approachable doesn't necessarily mean changing the language; rather, it means eliciting students' prior knowledge in pre-reading discussions, going over new vocabulary before reading, and having students complete tasks that are within their capabilities before they begin intensive reading.

2. The reading goal must be genuine; students must be reading for valid, personally relevant reasons. Reading a text "because the teacher assigned it" is not a valid justification.

Ask students how they intend to use the language they are learning and what subjects they are interested in reading and learning about in order to determine appropriate reading purposes. Allow students to select their reading assignments, and encourage them to use the library, the Internet, and bookstores and newsstands that sell publications in other languages to find other books they'd want to read.

3. The reading strategy must be genuine; students should read the text in a way that corresponds to the reading objective, the genre, and the manner in which people typically read. This implies that reading aloud will only occur in circumstances when it would occur outside of the classroom, such as while reading for enjoyment. The majority of the reading that pupils complete should be done aloud.

The degree of comprehension of a piece or text is referred to as reading comprehension. It's generally accepted that a reading speed of 200 to 220 words per minute is regarded to be average. A level of understanding of 75% is considered appropriate for average reading rates. This means that reading comprehension standards are considered to be met if a student can comprehend the meaning of at least 75% of the entire text provided.

Reading is an active activity that calls for the interaction of several different types of knowledge.

Listeners and readers use four different sorts of competences as they try to understand an oral or written communication, according to Canale and Swain's model of communicative competence.

1. grammatical competence: knowledge of morphology, syntax, vocabulary, and mechanics;
2. sociolinguistic competence: knowing what is expected socially and culturally by native speakers of the target language;
3. discourse competence: the ability to use cohesive devices such as pronouns, conjunctions, and transitional phrases to link meaning across sentences, as well as the ability to recognize how coherence is used to maintain the message's input;
4. strategic competence: the ability to use a number of guessing strategies to compensate for missing knowledge.

Readers rely upon the types of knowledge described above as they perform a variety of tasks in the comprehension process.

Conclusion. Reading is a purposeful activity. Decoding is only one part of reading comprehension. When the reader is aware of the reading objectives and is aware of the abilities and techniques that should be used to achieve those objectives, reading comprehension results. The capacity and confidence to handle communication problems they may encounter outside of the classroom are skills that instructors assist their students acquire by increasing students' awareness of reading as a skill that requires active participation and by explicitly teaching

reading methods. They provide their pupils with the building blocks for communicative proficiency in the new language in this way.

The list of used literature

1. Pearson, P. David. ["The Roots of Reading Comprehension Instruction"](#) University of California, Berkeley. Retrieved 15 March 2013.
2. Louisa C. Moats. ["Teaching Reading Is Rocket Science, American Federation of Teachers, Washington, DC, USA, 2020"](#) –p. 4
3. Goodman, Kenneth J. "Reading: A psycholinguistic guessing game". *Journal of the Reading Specialist*. 1967., 6 (4): -p. 126–135.
4. Stanislas Dehaene. [Reading in the brain](#). Penguin Books. 2010. pp. [327–328](#)